

HARMONICS MITIGATION IN A LARGE-SCALE GRID-CONNECTED FUEL CELL STACK

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Abstract:

A fuel cell inverter is a source of harmonics as its output voltage and current are not pure sine waves. A direct connection of such power unit into the grid may deteriorate the grid power quality and even affect its stability. Standards such as IEEE 519 and IEC 61000-3-6 set the current and the voltage harmonic distortion limits that a grid-connected power generating unit must not exceed, based on the current and voltage level. This paper deals with the design of an LCL filter to reduce harmonics produced by a three-level inverter serving as an interface between a fuel cell stack and a grid. The grid connected inverter is supplied from a 1.4 MW solid oxide fuel cell stack at 1400 V and operate at an efficiency of 86%. To assess the performance of the filter, the grid-connected system composed of a 1.4 MW fuel cell stack, an inverter, an LCL filter, a grid and a load is simulated using Matlab/Simulink environment. Results show that the designed filter reduces the total harmonic distortions of both voltage and current up to 0.01 %.

Keywords: Fuel cell, LCL filter, Three Level Diode Clamped Inverter.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The fuel cell inverter is a source of harmonics as its output voltage and current are not pure sine waves. These harmonics may affect sensitive equipment's above several kilowatts connected to the inverter [1]. Conventionally, the criteria used to reduce harmonics is the input inductance and the output inductance of the power conversion devices [2]. However, as the size of systems increase, realising practical filters becomes difficult due to the higher cost that maybe involved. Various types of filters such as a first-order L filter, a second order LC filter or a third-order LCL filter, etc. can be found [3]. However, the LCL filter is a preferred option for high power applications ranging from hundreds of kW to several MW [4]. In comparison with an L filter, an LCL filter has the advantage of achieving better attenuation capacity for complex harmonics and has better dynamic characteristics [5,6]. On the other hand, an LCL filter can cause instability problems as its zero impedance may create resonance at certain frequencies. To overcome the effect of LCL filter zero impedance, several damping techniques have been proposed such as incorporating a physical passive element in series with the filter capacitor [7,8]. The damping technique using a passive element is simple and reliable, but the passive element results in power

loss and weakens the effect of the LCL filter. To overcome this, active damping can be used [9].

This paper deals with the design of an LCL filter to reduce harmonics produced by a three-level inverter serving as an interface between a fuel cell stack and a grid in order to meet IEEE 519-2014 standards.

IEEE 519-2014 standards defines the allowable voltage total harmonic distortion in terms of voltage level, while the current total demand distortion limit is expressed as function of the voltage level and the ratio of the short circuit current to the rated load current (Table 1). Furthermore, IEEE 519-2014 defines the total harmonics distortion as the ratio of the root mean square of the harmonic content, considering harmonic components up to the 50th order and specifically excluding inter harmonics, expressed as a percent of the fundamental [4], while the total demand distortion is defined as the ratio of the root mean square of the harmonic content, considering harmonic components up to the 50th order and specifically excluding inter harmonics. At maximum rated power, both current total demand distortion and current total harmonic distortion are equal.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows section 2 is dedicated to the system description and filter modelling, section 3 deals with the simulation results and the last section presents the conclusion.

Table 1: IEEE 519-2014 Voltage at PCC [10]

Voltage at PCC	Individual harmonic (%)	THD
$V \leq 1.0 \text{ kV}$	5.0	8.0
$1 \text{ kV} < V \leq 68 \text{ kV}$	3.0	5.0
$69 \text{ kV} < V \leq 161 \text{ kV}$	1.5	2.5
$161 \text{ kV} < V$	1.0	1.5 ^a

Table 2: Current distortion limits according to IEEE 519-2014 [10]

Voltage <69 kV	I_{sc}/I_{load}	TDD (%)	Distortion Limits (%)			
			<11	11≤h <17	17≤h <35	35≤h <50
<20	5	4	2	1.5	0.6	
20 - 50	8	7	3.5	2.5	1	
50 - 100	12	10	4.5	4	1.5	
100 - 1000	15	12	5.5	5	2	
>1000	20	15	7	6	2.5	

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND FILTER MODELLING

2.1. System description

The layout of the proposed system is depicted in Fig. 1 and consists of the following main components: a fuel cell stack, an inverter, an LCL filter and a grid. The fuel cell generates 1.4 MW at 600 V. The DC link capacitor serves as input to the inverter and maintain the voltage of the DC bus to 600 V even in case there is a variation in the fuel cell side. The inverter is controlled through a voltage loop and a current loop control schemes, its output is connected to an LCL filter to mitigate harmonics. The output voltage of the inverter is about 1400 Volt between phases with a maximum power of 1.2 MW. The inverter parameters are given in Table 3

Fig. 1: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell [4]

Table 3: Inverter design parameters

Output DC power of Fuel cell P_{DC}	1.4 MW
DC-Link Voltage V_{DC}	1400 V
Output power of the Inverter V_{DC}	1.2 MW
line to line RMS voltage V_{LL}	600V
Phase voltage V_{PH}	346 V
Nominal current I_{rms}	1200 A
Power factor P_f	0.95
Peak to peak current I_{max}	1630.22 A
PWM carrier frequency I_{max}	2000 Hz
Grid frequency f_g	50 Hz
Modulation range m_a	0.7
Attenuation factor K_a	20%
Maximal power factor variation of the grid X	5%
Inverter configuration 3ϕ	Three-phase

2.2. Filter modelling

The design of three-phase LCL filter depicted in the equivalent circuit in Fig. 5 requires input parameters including the rated power of the inverter P_{rated} , the DC-link voltage V_{dc} , the grid frequency f_g , the switching frequency f_{sw} , the sampling frequency f_{samp} , and the rms of the grid voltage V_g .

The LCL filter parameters are given in Table 4 and Its design is carried out based on the algorithm in Fig.3 and using the following equations:

1. Critical frequency

The critical frequency ω_{crit} (f_{crit}) is defined by the following equations:

$$\omega_{crit} = \pi/3T_{samp} \quad (12)$$

$$f_{crit} = \frac{\pi}{3} f_{samp} \frac{1}{2\pi} = f_{samp}/6 \quad (13)$$

where T_{samp} and f_{samp} are the sampling period and sampling frequency respectively.

Fig. 2: Per-phase model of a 3-phase LCL filter
[11]

2. Resonance frequency

The resonance frequency f_{res} is selected as expressed in equation (14):

$$f_{res}/f_{samp} = 0.10 \sim 0.12 \quad (14)$$

Furthermore, the condition in equation (15) must always be verified [12].

$$10f_g < f_{res} < 0.5f_{sw} \quad (15)$$

3. Correlation constant

The correlation constant r between the converter and the grid side inductance is defined as follows:

$$L_g = rL_c \quad (16)$$

where L_g and L_c are the grid and converter inductance respectively.

In high power application, for minimum filter size, L_c and L_g must be selected to be the same ($r = 1$) [13].

4. Capacitor C_f

The capacitor C_f is obtained as follows [14]:

$$C_f = x \times \frac{P_{rated}}{3 \times 2\pi \times f_g \times V_g^2} \quad (18)$$

where x is reactive power absorption rate chosen in the interval between 0.01 and 0.05 [15].

5. Converter side inductance L_c and grid side inductance L_g

Equation (19) is used to compute the product $L_c \cdot C_f$ since f_{res} was determined in equation (14) and r is selected based on the filter design criterion.

$$f_{res} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{L_c + rL_g}{rL_cL_gC_f}} \quad (19)$$

From the product $L_c \cdot C_f$ and C_f in equation (18), L_c and L_g are acquired.

6. Current ripple Δi

The current ripple can be determined using equation (19) as follows [16] :

$$\Delta i = \frac{V_{dc}}{8L_c f_{sw}} \leq \left(\frac{Ripple\%}{100} \right) \times \hat{I}_f \quad (20)$$

The current ripple Δi should be limited in the range between 10 and 25% of the peak rated output current \hat{I}_f [14]. The correlation between the harmonics generated by the converter and the one injected into the grid is given in (21).

$$\frac{I_g(h_{sw})}{I_c(h_{sw})} = \frac{1}{|1 + r(1 - L_c C_b \omega_{sw}^2 x)|} \quad (21)$$

where $I_c(h_{sw})$ and $I_g(h_{sw})$ are the harmonics generated by the converter and the one injected into the grid respectively.

7. Damping resistor R_d

At the resonance frequency, the impedance of the LCL filter is equal to zero and the magnitude response tends to be very large. Therefore, R_d is added in series with C_f to provide a non-zero impedance, hence, limiting the resonance peaks. In general, R_d should be at least one third of C_f as shown in equation (22) [12].

$$R_d \geq \frac{1}{3\omega_{res}C_f} \quad (22)$$

Fig.3: LCL filter design algorithm

Table 4: LCL-Filter parameters

LCL-Filter	
Parameter	Value
Inverter Side inductor L_c	0.8 mH
Grid Side inductor L_g	0.8 mH
Capacitor filter C_f	531 μ F
Damping Resistor R_d	0.118 Ω
Resonant frequency f_{res}	845 Hz
Inductor resistances $R_i = R_g$	0.00761 Ω
Sampling frequency f_{smp}	10000 Hz
Crossover frequency f_c	254 Hz

III. SIMULATION, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system in Fig. 1 was simulated using MATLAB/Simulink tool based on parameters in Tables 3 and 4 to assess the performance of the designed LCL filter in reducing harmonics, while the system is operating at its full rated power.

The phase-to-phase voltage of the 3-level inverter before introducing the filter is shown in Fig.4. The RMS value is around 919 V with a high Total Harmonics Distortion of about 52.74 % as shown in Fig.5, while the total harmonic distortion of the current is 51.61% as depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 4: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

Fig. 5: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

Fig. 6: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

Fig. 7: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

On the other, the phase-to-phase voltage and the phase current at the output of the filter are shown in Fig. 7. with the RMS value of the voltage and the current equal respectively to 600 V and 1200. Both the voltage and the current show reduced total harmonic distortions of up to 0.01% as shown in histograms in Fig.8 and Fig.9

Fig. 8: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

Fig. 9: Layout of a grid connected fuel cell

The obtained values complies with the IEEE 519-2014 standards which defines the harmonic distortion limit for voltages less than 1 kV to 8 % (Table1), while the total demand distortion limit for voltages less than 69 kV and currents greater than 1000 A is limited to 20 % (Table 2).

Additionally, the results obtained in this study are compared against previous research on LCL filters as shown in Table 5. The comparison reveals that the

obtained total harmonics distortions are lower than the ones proposed in previous studies.

Table 5: LCL filter results comparison

Studies conducted	[17]	[18]	[19]	[20]	This study
Multilevel inverter	3-level NPC	3-level NPC	-	5-level NPC	3-level NPC
DC Voltage (V)	-	750	1500	400	1400
AC Voltage (V)	-	220	1200	283	600
Power (kW)	-	30	1500	5	1300
Switching Frequency (kHz)		5	5	10	2
THD of voltage (%)	1.27	-	-	0.33%	0.01%
THD of current (%)	2.41	-	-	-	0.01%

IV. CONCLUSION

A fuel cell inverter is a source of harmonics as its output voltage and current are not pure sine waves. A direct connection of such power unit into the grid may deteriorate the grid power quality and even affect its stability. This paper dealt with the design of an LCL filter to reduce harmonics produced by a three-level inverter serving as an interface between a fuel cell stack and a grid. IEEE 519 standards set the harmonic distortion limits for voltages less than 1 kV to 8 %, while the total demand distortion limit for voltages less than 69 kV and currents greater than 1000 A is limited to 20 %. The results show that the designed filter complied with the above-mentioned standards by reducing the total harmonic distortion to 0.01 % and 0.01 % for the voltage and the current, respectively.

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